

1. General Information

Title: Creative Problem-Solving: A Study with Blind and Low-Vision Software Professionals

Date Created: S2 2024

Researchers involved: Karina Kohl, Yoonha Cha, Victoria Jackson, Rafael Prikladnicki, André van der Hoek, Stacy Branham

Context/Scope:

The study explores the innovative strategies employed by BLVSPs to overcome these accessibility barriers, focusing on their custom solutions and the importance of supportive communities. We conducted semi-structured interviews with 30 Blind and Low-Vision Software Professionals who worked in software engineering positions in corporate settings or as freelancers. Participants were recruited through professional contacts, specialized mailing lists like Program-L, and snowball sampling. Interviews were conducted via Zoom between May and July 2024, with audio recorded. Participants reviewed study materials and completed a demographic survey before interviews. Questions focused on workplace accessibility challenges, use of existing solutions, tool development, and experiences sharing tools with colleagues. Each participant received \$40/hour compensation via gift card. The study was approved by the researcher's Institutional Review Board (IRB).

2. Codebook

2.1. Motivation Driven by Need

Necessity drives creativity in BLVSPs, where the need for autonomy and better tools sparks intrinsic motivation to solve problems, often leading to the development of custom solutions.

2.1.1. Add-ons are built because something at work does not work

"A few of these add-ons were developed because we were complaining about something in our professional lives that didn't work well." (P7)

2.1.2. When you are the first to create a tool, there are big chances of someone making a better version.

"I think I'm the first person to do something like this. If you're the first person to build a product of whatever it is, like, chances are that someone's going to come along, see that, and make a better version. And I'm cool with that, you know?" (P24)

2.2. Creation of Opportunities

BLVSPs turn personal challenges into collective innovation, with motivation driving individual solutions and broader organizational benefits, such as leveraging the latest technology for accessibility.

2.2.1. Find out a way to reframe a problem in a way that can benefit the entire team

"You just have to frame the problem in a way that is, you know, that is going to benefit the rest of the team." (P24)

2.3. Creation of Tools

BLVSPs' drive to improve their work environment fuels creative solutions, from optimizing to developing tools that enhance workplace autonomy and professional presence, tackling both accessibility and professional challenges.

2.3.1. Built a tool using Computer Vision to help with the environment around

"One of the big things originally started out as describe this image; describe the entire screen. But now, it... I got a lot of feedback from people. Actually, more feedback than I ever thought I'd get for something that I just use for work. And so, I ended up building another feature into it." (P7)

2.4. Use and Customization of Tools

BLVSPs leverage deep technical knowledge to adapt and enhance existing tools, overcoming accessibility barriers and maintaining productivity, as demonstrated through custom solutions.

2.4.1. Customize settings of Nav add-on

"With the Indent Nav add-on that I was talking about, you can customize the different beeps that it makes for how many lines it skips through." (P7)

2.4.2. Customize Speech History add-on to track if someone used the computer

"I modified this speech history add-on to write everything that happened to disk. All of the speech items. So, I could lock my computer; leave it locked to the desk with a trusty pad lock. And if anyone actually pressed any keys, I would know exactly which keys they pressed based on the screen reader's reaction to it." (P7)

2.5. Workflow Strategies

For BLVSPs, creativity primarily involves adapting their workflows, using domain skills to repurpose tools and processes to overcome accessibility barriers, rather than traditional artifact creation.

2.5.1. Did not create DIY tools but created strategies and processes to help in daily tasks

"What I did is set some techniques, some tricks, that over time I managed a way how to be more effective to switch between windows if there are multiple windows opened. How to really manage my emails, like how many

instances I should keep open and how those things... so... Sometimes those are the more effective steps I adopted." (P5)

2.5.2. If something is not accessible try to do it via the Command line

"If UI is not accessible, then it's always challenging for me to use, right? So, I always try to figure out how to do the same thing via Command Line comments." (P5)

2.5.3. Try to find workarounds or alternative open-source software when tools are not accessible and companies do not want to fix them

"If they're not, then I'll just use my own tools, or workarounds, and I'll tell them, okay, this is how I'll do it. And usually, if they're using like a proprietary software, there's like an open source alternative, or something, that does something, like, that does similar things. Then I'll just use those. And then try to get it done." (P13)

2.5.4. When the world is not designed for people like you you are constantly looking for a workaround

"If you live in a world that hasn't been designed for people like you and you're constantly having to come up with, you know, workarounds from a really, really young age, you know?" (P24)

2.6. Communities, Sharing, Publicize

BLVSPs are motivated to share solutions with a strong community-driven, and open-source spirit fostering innovation.

2.6.1. Feels great about the tool created because it helps other people

"I think it's pretty exhilarating. It's pretty satisfying because not only was this working – it wasn't just for me." (P13)

2.6.2. NVDA requires add-ons to be OSS

"So, there are like settings that pretty much every add-on has that you can configure as a user. But then, if that add-on doesn't do something that you want, since add-ons are required to be open source, based on NVDA's license, you can just create an issue on Git Hub for it." (P7)

2.6.3. Add-on spread pretty much all word-of-mouth

"It was pretty much all word of mouth. I feel like I just woke up one morning, and it had like 30-some stars on Git Hub. I don't remember really saying much of anything." (P7)

2.6.4. Lessons learned: publicize and get media attention to help more people

"I'd definitely put it in more places. I think there might be some opportunity to maybe even get some potential media interest, or something like that out of it. Because my goal isn't to make money off of it. It's purely to try to put it in the hands of as many people as possible." (P7)